

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Attitude analysis of traditional food products by millennial consumers: A study of Jenang products in Kudus regency

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Abstract

Jenang kudu is a specialty food from Kudus-Indonesia, one of the products of the agribusiness system from upstream to downstream, starting from the processing of raw materials from rice flour, sugar, and coconut milk, to the product marketing process. Jenang kudu has been designated as one of Indonesia's Intangible Cultural Heritage (WBTH) in 2022 by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia, but the attitude of the millennial generation in Kudus Regency towards jenang kudu is still low. The purpose of this study was to analyze the attitude of millennial consumers in Kudus Regency towards jenang kudu. This research was conducted at the largest and oldest producer of jenang kudu from August to October 2024. The research was conducted by survey and interview. The sampling technique used was non probability sampling which was determined by accidental sampling, then continued with purposive sampling because the target was millennials aged 23-42 years with the criteria that millennial consumers in Kudus who purchased jenang kudu at the research location at least twice. Determination of the number of respondent samples using the Nunnally method with a sample size of 70 respondents. The data analysis used is Fishbein analysis with a Likert scale. The results of attitude analysis show that millennial consumers towards jenang kudu show a positive attitude.

Keywords: Attitude; Millennial Consumer; Jenang Kudus; Marketing mix; Fishbein

1. Introduction

Traditional food is food or drink prepared using traditional recipes and methods passed down from one generation to the next. Each region in Indonesia has its own distinctive and varied traditional culinary products. These foods are important elements in the culture and culinary heritage of local communities, reflecting the diversity of Indonesian cuisine and also have significant historical and cultural value (Harsana and Triwidayati, 2020). Various regions in Indonesia are known for their traditional foods, such as rendang from Padang, kerak telur from Betawi, satay from Madura, gudeg from Yogyakarta, opak from Sukabumi, jenang from Kudus, and many others. Each region has traditional specialties that have unique flavors and characteristics. This traditional food is a crucial element of a region's culinary identity and often attracts tourists who want to taste the culinary (Nugroho and Hardani, 2020). Traditional foods have characteristics, namely recipes that are passed down from generation to generation, the use of certain traditional equipment in food processing (for example, dishes must be processed with clay tools), and processing techniques that must be carried out in order to achieve the unique taste and appearance of a dish (Astuti et al., 2023).

Jenang kudu is one of the products of the agribusiness system from upstream to downstream, starting from the processing of raw materials from coconut milk, sugar, and sticky rice flour, to the product marketing process. Jenang kudu is a traditional food originating from Kudus Regency, Central Java, Indonesia which has been named one of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Indonesia in 2022 by the Indonesian Ministry of Research, Technology and Higher Education. Jenang kudu has a variety of flavors including original, durian, mocha, chocolate, grape, sesame,

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and others. Currently, the majority of jenang kudu consumers are elderly people, while millennial consumers in Kudus Regency are less interested in jenang kudu. As we know that the millennial generation has the largest population today and they are already less interested in traditional food products, one of which is jenang kudu. This is certainly a special concern that will be discussed in this topic related to analyzing attitudes towards traditional food products in Kudus Regency which have begun to decline in popularity, especially among the millennial generation. This analysis uses the Fishbein multi-attribute model to measure the attitudes of millennial consumers in Kudus Regency towards jenang kudu in the hope that it can be used as a reference for producers and local governments to innovate and strive for digitalization as a means of marketing so that it also has an impact on the economy of the people in Kudus Regency. In addition, this research can be used as a scientific study of research on the potential of jenang kudu in the future, considering that there is still very little literature and topics that raise the traditional food of jenang kudu.

Kudus Regency has the ability to attract tourists, who come to explore the culture and specialties of the region. In this case, it is crucial to know the extent to which traditional culinary products such as jenang play a role in attracting the attention and interest of millennial consumers visiting Kudus Regency. Kudus is recognized as a prime location for the manufacture of the famous jenang. Jenang kudu provides a wide selection of authentic and delicious jenang (Indonesia Kaya, 2022). Jenang is a traditional Indonesian food made from steamed glutinous rice mixed with sugar, coconut milk, and various additives such as nuts, sesame, or fruits (Gardjito et al., 2019). Jenang kudu has a unique flavor and quality that has been preserved for a long time, making it one of the most sought-after and appreciated traditional foods (Telusur, 2022). Jenang kudu has been officially recognized as one of Indonesia's Intangible Cultural Heritage (WBTH) in 2022 by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia.

Attitudes can influence consumer behavior in choosing products, so it is very important to know how attitudes are formed and how companies can change or use them to increase sales. Consumer attitudes are a crucial element that influences their choices (Widiana and Putri, 2021). Attitudes reflect consumers' emotions towards a product, whether they like it or not. This study adopts the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as the theoretical basis for deeply understanding individual behavior. According to Azjen (1991), this theory can be used to explain an individual's desire to buy a product. A person's interest in doing tends to increase if there is a positive attitude, support from the surrounding environment, and a feeling of comfort (Kuncoro et al., 2022).

Attitude is the main factor that influences a person's interest in buying. Fishbein and Ajzen state that a person's attitude determines whether they will give a positive or negative response and whether they will accept or reject an assessment of a product or object. Consumer interest and decisions in making purchases will increase if consumers show a good attitude. The limitation of shopping interest is strongly influenced by consumer behavior (Mulasakti and Mas'ud, 2020). Attitude is an evaluation of a person's positive or negative beliefs or feelings if they have to do the behavior to be determined, before doing this behavior, they must consider whether this behavior can have a positive or negative effect on entrepreneurial interest, (Khafidah et al., 2023). This study examines the attitude of the millennial generation towards jenang kudu. The lack of interest of the millennial generation in the traditional food of jenang kudu is a topic discussed in this study through attitude analysis.

Generation Y, often called the millennial generation, is a group of individuals born between 1981 and 2000 (Jatmika and Puspitasari, 2019). Millennials often get information about food and beverages through social media and digital platforms, which greatly influences their choices. The discrepancy between millennial consumers and traditional food producers is an important issue, as millennials prefer foods that are practical, innovative, and labeled "healthy" or "organic" (Fasha and Yuwono, 2022). This may affect their attitudes towards jenang kudu. Elements such as quality image, brand image, price, accessibility, and product promotion also play a significant role in influencing millennials' purchase interest in traditional food products (Wiandana and Suryani, 2020). Millennials are increasingly showing great interest in modern and fast food trends. However, they tend to view traditional food as a less attractive or outdated option. This generation prioritizes health and convenience, resulting in a decline in traditional food consumption. For example, research reveals that millennials tend to choose fast food over traditional cooking methods that take longer (Anshari et al., 2019). Research shows that millennials are more likely to engage with brands that make good use of social commerce, which often emphasizes old-school food trends over traditional culinary practices (Ramnarain et al., 2024). In addition, product attributes, purchase motivations and psychologically appealing digital marketing are critical and can shape individuals' preferences in purchasing traditional foods (Contini et al., 2016).

This study is expected to provide strategic direction for producers, local governments and other relevant parties in supporting the promotion and preservation of this traditional food, by understanding the elements that influence millennials' interest in jenang kudu. Furthermore, the millennial generation's positive attitude towards jenang kudu is expected to have a positive impact on their buying interest. It is also expected to maintain the sustainability and

diversity of traditional culinary in Kudus Regency. the purpose of this study is to analyze the attitudes of millennial consumers in Kudus Regency towards jenang kudu.

2. Material and methods

The method applied in this research is a quantitative approach with a survey strategy. Quantitative research method is a type of research that utilizes statistics and numbers in the process of collecting and analyzing measurable data. The research locations are the three largest and oldest producers in Kudus Regency, which are still continuously producing and innovating. Data sources include primary data and secondary data. Primary data include the results of closed questionnaires and interviews, while secondary data are taken from literature that supports the research results. This research uses a Likert scale measurement method with a score of 1 - 4, score 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (agree), and 4 (strongly agree).

The population in this study consisted of millennials aged between 23 and 42 years in Kudus Regency. The sampling technique applied was non probability sampling. Determination of respondents was carried out accidentally, namely researchers found respondents accidentally when potential respondents bought jenang. Furthermore, the research continued with purposive sampling, because the target was millennials aged 23 to 42 years with the criteria of residents of Kudus Regency domicile, consumers who made direct offline purchases, and consumers who had bought jenang kudu at least twice. The number of respondents used in this study was 70 respondents.

Attitude analysis using fishbein multiattribute analysis with the following attribute model :

$$A_o = \sum_{i=1}^n (b_i)(e_i)$$

Keterangan:

- A_o = attitude towards an object
- b_i = strength of belief/belief that the object has attribute i
- e_i = evaluation of attribute i
- n = number of attributes the object has

The results of the assessment of the attitudes of respondents, especially millennial consumers towards jenang kudu (e_i, b_i), are classified into four categories, namely very negative, negative, positive, and very positive. The following is the scale calculation and interval table for the attitude category.

Table 1 Attitude Score Category

Scale	Attitude score	Range Score
1	Strongly Negative	$1,00 \leq A_0 \leq 4,74$
2	Negative	$4,75 < A_0 \leq 8,50$
3	Positive	$8,50 < A_0 \leq 12,25$
4	Strongly Positive	$12,25 < A_0 \leq 16$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Jenang Kudus

Jenang kudu is a traditional food originating from Kudus Regency, Central Java. It is made with ingredients such as glutinous rice flour, granulated sugar, brown sugar and coconut milk. In addition, some producers also include additional ingredients such as durian, mocha and chocolate for certain flavor variations. Based on a study conducted by Putri et al. (2022), the raw materials used in making jenang Kudus have a major influence on the quality and taste of the resulting product. The characteristics of the glutinous rice flour used include white color, no odor, free of lice, and not mixed with flour or other objects. The characteristics of coconut raw materials used are coconuts of the Ubud variety,

Bali. The coconuts selected should be old, the shell is not broken, the coconut water is odorless, and the coconut meat is not slimy. The granulated sugar used is pure white, free from lice, and the granules are not crushed. The characteristics of brown sugar used are coconut sap sugar, dark brown in color, without much pulp attached, and does not melt easily.

The process of making jenang starts with preparing the ingredients, namely glutinous rice flour, granulated sugar, coconut sugar, brown sugar and coconut milk. The glutinous rice flour required for one crater is 120 kilograms. Heating stage I is carried out by heating granulated sugar, brown sugar, crushed sugar, and coconut milk stirring until all ingredients dissolve. After that, the filtering process is carried out to separate the sugar solution from any impurities. Next, the crater is thoroughly cleaned and proceeds to cooking stage II by mixing the glutinous rice flour mixture and coconut milk into the sugar solution produced from cooking process I. Stirring is done continuously to ensure the batter is well mixed and reduce the chance of crust formation or caramelization. The cooking temperature ranges from 120 degrees Celsius to 130 degrees Celsius. Next, the mixture is added with sesame seeds, margarine, essences and vanilla. Jenang that has reached 80% maturity will proceed to the sampling stage to be tested for quality in accordance with the company's standards, i.e. free from the mixture of other ingredients, appropriate moisture content, and manual organoleptic testing. This is followed by the cutting and packaging stages. Along with technological advances, a number of jenang kudus industries have begun to apply machinery in their production processes. For example, the utilization of effective coconut milk squeezers and large mixing machines to mix the dough. The aim of this is to improve work efficiency, reduce dependence on human labor, and ensure consistent product quality.

3.2. Respondent Characteristics

The consumer behavior of millennials in Indonesia towards traditional food is influenced by demographic factors, including age, gender, and education level. Based on the findings of the 2020 Population Census conducted by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Indonesia's population structure by generation is as follows: Pre-Boomers (born before 1945) totaling 5.03 million people (1.87%); Baby Boomers (born 1946-1964) totaling 31.01 million people (11.56%); Generation X (born 1965-1980) totaling 58.65 million people (21.88%); Millennials (born 1981-2000), 74.93 million (27.94%); Generation Z (born 2001-2012), 69.38 million (25.87%); and Post-Gen Z (born after 2013), 29.17 million (10.88%).

Figure 1 2020 Population Census by Statistics Indonesia

This data shows that the millennial generation is the largest group in Indonesia's population, reaching 74.93 million or around 27.94% of the total population. The structure of the population by generation is crucial to understanding the social and economic dynamics in Indonesia. Demographic elements play a significant role in millennial consumers' lack of buying interest in traditional Indonesian cuisine. Millennials, born between 1981 and 2000, are currently in the productive age phase and have considerable purchasing power. Although they are numerous, their propensity to choose traditional food is low. A study conducted by Hasriyani (2021) in Ajibata Sub-district, Toba Samosir Regency, indicated that millennials have a greater interest in using technological devices and obtaining information through social media platforms, so their exposure to traditional food is very limited.

Figure 2 Last education of Kudus District residents

The latest education of the Kudus jenang consumers in this study consisted of 70 respondents, of which 42 people had an education level \geq D3 / D4 / S1 Equivalent, 21 people had SMA / MA Equivalent, 4 people had SMP / MTs Equivalent, and 3 people had SD / MI Equivalent. Education has a significant influence on consumer decisions and purchases. This is in line with the opinion of Mahendra and Ardani (2024) who state that consumers with higher levels of education are able to assess products better, especially in the category of natural cosmetics, so that the decisions made become more logical. This study reveals that education, especially at the middle and higher levels, increases consumers' ability to make rational and appropriate decisions. Therefore, education plays an important role in shaping preferences and consumption patterns.

Figure 3 Monthly income of Kudus District residents

The amount of income of millennial consumers related to jenang kudus in this study consists of: Rp > 1,000,000 as many as 7 people, and Rp 1,000,000 - Rp 3,000,000 as many as 40 people. Individual income can affect buying interest, where the higher a person's income, the greater their interest in buying traditional foods such as jenang kudus. This is in line with the opinion of Singh and Verma (2017) who state that several factors that influence individual buying interest in traditional foods include adequate knowledge, sufficient income, and aspects of hygiene and health, such as the absence of chemicals in traditional foods.

3.3. Fishbein Multiattribute Analysis

Attitude is the main factor that can influence a person's interest in taking an action. Simanihuruk's statement (2020) explains that a person's attitude can influence his interest in carrying out an action. Attitude towards behavior aims to assess the extent to which the performance of the behavior can be considered positive or negative to be appreciated.

According to Kusumawaty et al. (2019) this consists of two parts, namely beliefs which are the level of consumer confidence when buying a product, and evaluations which are assessments that arise from within consumers after they buy the product. In this study, attitude consists of the two components mentioned above.

Based on the results of the Fishbein multiattribute model analysis, the consumer attitude variable reflects the level of belief in four attributes. This variable shows how consumers assess the level of trust in the four attributes of jenang kudus, namely product, price, location, and promotion. Table 2 shows the average beliefs and assessments of millennial consumers on the attributes studied.

Table 2 Millennial Consumers' Belief and Evaluation Levels of Jenang Kudus

Attribute	bi	Category	Attribute	ei	Category
Product	3,39	Strongly Agree	Product	3,37	Strongly Agree
Price	3,41	Strongly Agree	Price	3,32	Strongly Agree
Place	3,00	Agree	Place	3,01	Agree
Promotion	2,33	Disagree	Promotion	2,30	Disagree

Source: Researcher Data, 2024

In accordance with the findings contained in Table 2, it can be concluded that consumer beliefs and assessments of product attributes show the highest value, with an average of 3.39 and 3.37, respectively. The values obtained are classified as significant in the aspects of belief and assessment in the Fishbein attribute model. This shows that millennial consumers agree that the product attributes of jenang kudus play a role in shaping millennial consumers' beliefs about their interest in purchasing jenang kudus, especially related to quality, taste, packaging, and product information. This statement is in line with what was conveyed by Risdianto et al. (2017), the main factor that is considered and can influence consumer buying interest is product quality.

The results showed that the level of consumer confidence and assessment of the promotion attribute was at the lowest position, with an average value of 2.33 and 2.30, respectively. This shows that kudus jenang producers have not carried out promotions effectively. Until now, companies that produce jenang kudus have carried out promotions through websites, Shopee, and Instagram. Meanwhile, other producers have not yet implemented digital promotions. Although producers have started to utilize digital platforms for marketing, the appearance of these platforms is still unattractive. In addition, producers are also lacking in promoting these platforms, so this has not been successful in attracting the attention of millennials in Kudus Regency. Based on the opinion of Santoso et al. (2020), promotions carried out through digital marketing can affect the level of consumer trust and interest in buying a product.

Millennial consumers' self-beliefs and evaluations of jenang kudus indicate that product characteristics strongly influence millennial consumers' attitudes towards jenang kudus. As explained by Mahendra and Ardani (2024), millennials pay special attention to product quality, especially when they buy traditional foods that have cultural and emotional value. Research conducted by Kusuma (2023) shows that product quality has a greater influence on millennial consumer loyalty than price. According to Harjayanti et al. (2020) stated that millennial groups tend to choose high-quality products, especially those that are of local origin and have real value. A study conducted by Ramadhani et al. (2021) explains that products with excellent quality provide benefits to consumers, especially in a highly competitive market for similar products. Consumers' self-confidence and opinions about jenang kudus clearly reflect that millennials highly value quality and authenticity, making the product a major factor in their purchasing decisions.

Table 3 Millennial Consumer Attitudes towards Jenang Kudus

Attribute	bi	ei	Ao	Score
Product	3.39	3.37	11.40	Positive
Price	3.41	3.32	11.33	Positive
Place	3.00	3.01	9.03	Positive
Promotion	2.33	2.30	5.34	Negative
$\Sigma (bi.ei)$			37.10	Positive

Source: Researcher Data, 2024

The assessment of consumer attitudes towards the characteristics of jenang kudu can be calculated by multiplying the average belief (bi) and evaluation (ei) values. If the attitude value for each attribute is summed up, the consumer attitude analysis value (bi. ei) will be obtained as well as the total result of the millennial consumer attitude value towards holy jenang (Ao). Table 3 presents the calculation of millennial consumers' attitudes towards jenang kudu. Product, price, and location attributes related to jenang kudu have attitude values of 11.40; 11.12; and 8.87, respectively, which are included in the positive attitude category. Consumers agree that each attribute based on the aspects studied through Fishbein's multiattribute analysis can influence the attitudes of millennial consumers regarding their interest in buying jenang kudu. The attitude value (Ao) of an attribute has a direct relationship with its effect on purchase intention. The higher the attitude value of an attribute, the greater the attention given by consumers to that attribute in purchasing decisions. In accordance with research conducted by Cheng et al. (2011) interest in buying is influenced by consumer attitudes; the more positive the value of consumer attitudes, the more their purchase intention increases. This statement is supported by Clarissa et al. (2018), the consideration rating can be assessed based on the attitude value (Ao). The higher the attitude value (Ao), the more likely the attribute is to be the main factor considered in consumers' purchase intention. The promotional attribute for jenang kudu has an attitude value of 5.31, which is included in the negative category. This indicates that promotional attributes are not able to influence consumer attitudes.

Millennials in shopping place more emphasis on product properties and prices, while promotions are considered less important and even have a negative impact. Based on the opinion of Widyastuti and Widagda (2021), product attributes have a significant influence on purchasing decisions, especially among consumers who care about quality and those who want distinctive characteristics. Research conducted by Harjayanti et al. (2020) shows that promotions have little impact on millennials and other rational consumers. These findings suggest that product features are highly influential on millennial customers' positive views of jenang kudu, emphasizing the importance of product quality and relevance in marketing strategies.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research that has been conducted, it is concluded that the attitude of millennial consumers in Kudus Regency towards jenang kudu shows a positive view of product attributes, price, and location, while for promotional attributes, the attitude tends to be negative. The suggestion that can be given is that jenang kudu producers must utilize promotions and start being active in digital marketing as a step to increase the buying interest of millennial consumers in Kudus Regency in jenang kudu products.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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